

2015

APR-MAY

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education
Research Journal (AMIERJ)***

***(Bi-Monthly)
Peer-Reviewed Journal
Impact factor: 0.948***

V O L - I V I s s u e s : I I I

Chief-Editor:

Ubale Amol Baban

**A STUDY OF THE PERCEPTION OF COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH REFERENCE TO
THE USE OF E-BANKING TECHNOLOGIES**

*** Anson L Albuquerque**

Research Scholar

Goa University

Address: B F3 Suyash Gardens Vidhyanagar

Margao Salcete

South-Goa Goa

**** Dr. Anthony Rodrigues**

Associate Professor

Goa University

Address: Department Of Commerce

Fr. Agnel College Of Arts And Commerce

Pilar-Goa.403203

Abstract

This study attempts to explore the new sources regarding Internet Banking and usage of Internet Banking Services. As we are all aware that college going students are all usually computer savy and using latest technological devices like mobile phones, laptops, tablets etc. as their way of life. This study assesses the perception of the college students with reference to the use of E-Banking Technologies in Banks. The survey was conducted during the month of November, 2014 among the students pursuing B.com. An analysis demonstrates that college students play a very important role in the use of E-Banking Technologies in Banks in the near future if the banks take adequate measures to promote the same among the students.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today banks play a very vital role in every individual's life. Banks services are being extended to remote areas as well as a very large customer base for which it is not possible for the

banks to still continue with their age old banking ways. Hence E-Banking Technologies plays an important role to the Banking Industry as well as to the customers. Banks henceforth have introduced a huge amount of capital into adopting newer and better technologies but the big question is why is it that there are still less number of user adopting the new E-Banking Technologies.

2. NEED OF THE STUDY

The use of E- Technology in the banking industry has immensely benefited various banks in India. Productivity enhancement, innovative products, speedy and seamless fund transfers, real time information and efficient risk management are some of the many advantages derived through the use of E – Technology in banking.

The need of studying the above given topic arises

- E- Technology provides many advantages to the customers, but it is still not used very effectively
- Whether the college students are well aware of various E-Technologies used by various banks, various precautionary measures to avoid frauds and its benefits to the customers, banks and the environment.
- Individual difference, computer literacy and different other variables reflect the customers intention.
- Since the students of today are well versed with banking and technology and are supposed to be using the E-Technology extensively it is important to study the student's perception about E-Banking Technology.

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The banking industry has adopted various E-Banking Technologies like INTERNET BANKING, MOBILE BANKING, TELEBANKING, ATM BANKING. Hence this study titled, “A STUDY OF THE PERCEPTION OF COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH REFERENCE TO THE USE OF E-BANKING TECHNOLOGY” is undertaken with the following objectives:

1. To understand various E-Banking Technologies introduced by banks
2. To assess the perception of college students towards use of this E-Technology
3. To suggest measures to the Banking Industry as to how can they improve their reach of E-Technology to the youth and effectively improve its use.

3.1 E-BANKING SERVICES OFFERED BY BANKS

1. Electronic Payment System (e-cheques)
2. Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS)
3. Electronic Fund Transfer
4. Electronic Clearing Service (ECS)
5. Automated Teller Machines
6. Telebanking Facility
7. Point of Sale Terminal (POS, Green Channel Counter)
8. Interactive Voice Response (IVR)
9. Short Message Service (SMS)
10. Internet Banking
11. Mobile Banking (SMS, GPRS AND ANDROID APP BASED)

3.2 BENIFITS OF THE USE OF E-TECHNOLOGY IN BANKS

3.2.1. Convenience:

Unlike banking branches situated around the corner of our homes and office places, online banking never closes. This facility is available 24×7 and not only that it's just a click of a mouse away. This service differs a bit with regards to the SSL encryption and the various other facilities on the internet banking from banks to banks, but the basic platform is the same.

3.2.2. Ubiquity / Portability:

If we are out of state of even country and there arises a need to operate your account, the facility of online banking and mobile banking can be used anywhere across the globe.

3.2.3. *Transaction Speed:*

Online Banking, ATM, Green Channel Counters execute and confirm a transaction at a

3.2.4.

much faster rate. Which allows a customer to withdraw or pay money from or to his account in real time.

3.2.5. Effectiveness:

Many online banking sites now offer sophisticated but user friendly tools including account aggregation, stock quotes, rates alerts and portfolio managing to manage our liquid assets more efficiently.

3.3 LIMITATIONS OF THE USE OF E-BANKING TECHNOLOGY

3.3.1 Startup may take time:

Opening a bank account online takes less than 5 minutes. But the initial procedure of than submitting the application, Snaps, Signatures and KYC documents maybe a little time consuming. This initial process of registration for Banking User ID and passwords may take a little time.

3.3.2 Trusting as it is virtual:

One of the biggest challenges on the banks part is to get the customer to trust their system. Customer are used to physical cash and paper receipts which is not the case in case of E-Banking Technologies.

3.3.3 Impersonal:

E-Banking Technologies offer very prompt and speedy services but it is virtual and no contact with humans which some customers prefer.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study has been undertaken to assess the opinion of college going students of GVM's College towards the use of E- Technology in Banks. All the respondents covered are students of B.com having knowledge and some having bank accounts. The students opinion on factors like cost effectiveness, saving of time, convenience, reliability, secrecy, accessibility etc. are covered under the study. The study is conducted from a consumer's point of view i.e. the students and not from the banks point of view as such the study is restricted to retail banking.

1. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

5.1 PRIMARY DATA

Survey method has been used for collecting primary data. A survey was carried out through a self-developed structured questionnaire.

5.2 SAMPLE SIZE

A sample size of 250 respondents was considered for the purpose of study.

2. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY

Table: 6.1. Frequency of the respondents aware using E-Banking

Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Frequently	28	11.20
Sometimes	167	66.80
Once or Twice	55	22.00
Total	250	100

Source: Primary Data

The table shows that 11.20% of the 250 students have frequently heard or have used some of the E-Banking Technologies whereas 66.80% have sometimes heard of this term and 22% have heard about it very rarely. So this means if E-Banking Technology has to be encouraged and put to optimum use a lot more awareness is to be brought.

Table: 6.2. E-Banking Facilities heard or used by respondents

E-Banking Services	No. of Frequency of Resp.	Percentage
ATM Card / Debit Card	248	99.20
Credit Card	26	10.40
Bill Payment	67	26.80

NEFT / RTGS	24	9.60
SMS Alerts	194	77.60
E- Shopping	20	8.00
Mobile Banking	113	45.20
Online Banking	130	52.00
Online D-mat Account	3	1.20

Source: Primary Data

The table indicates that 99.20% of the students are aware about the facilities of the ATM/Debit Card, so now the banks need to greatly promote Facilities of Credit Card, NEFT/RTGS, E-Shopping, Bill Payment, Online D-Mat and also improve the awareness of its Mobile Banking, Online Banking and SMS Banking.

TABLE: 6.3. AWARENESS OF THE ADVANTAGES OF E-BANKING TECHNOLOGIES

Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage
To a Large Extent	5	2.00
To Some Extent	212	84.80
A Small Extent	33	13.20
Total	250	100.00

Source: Primary Data

This table depicts that a very small % i.e. hardly 2% students are fully aware about the Advantages of E-Banking Technologies and majority of the students i.e. 84.80% have a more or less idea and 13.20% students lack about the benefits and usefulness of E-Banking Technologies. Hence banks have to stress more about the advantages as the customer needs to know in what way he will benefit.

TABLE: 6.4. WHETHER USE OF E-BANKING TECHNOLOGIES IS A CUSTOMER

Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage
To a Large Extent	108	43.20
To Some Extent	126	50.40

A Small Extent	16	6.40
Total	250	100.00

Source: Primary Data

This study shows that 43.20% of the students are very much in favor that adoption of E-Banking Technology benefits the customer cost-wise where as 50.40% know it benefits but aren't sure of how exactly it does and 6.40% of the students feel it does not play a significant role for a customer cost-wise. But since it does play a significant role the customer need to be made aware in what way are they going to benefit cost-wise.

TABLE: 6.5. DIFFERENT WAYS THAT E-BANKING TECHNOLOGIES INCREASE THE CONVENIENCE OF CUSTOMERS.

Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage
To a Large Extent	19	7.60
To Some Extent	189	75.60
A Small Extent	42	16.80
Total	250	100.00

Source: Primary Data

The study depicts that 7.60% of the students are pretty much aware of the ways E-Banking increases the convenience of a customer whereas 75.60% believe to some extent and 16.80% believe that it may or may not play a major role. Hence banks will have to build up strategies in helping customers realize and witness the convenience caused when such Technology is adopted.

TABLE: 6.6. E-BANKING TECHNOLOGIES INCREASES ACCESSIBILITY TO BANKS ANYTIME AND ANYWHERE

Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage
To a Large Extent	219	87.60
To Some Extent	29	11.60
A Small Extent	2	0.80
Total	250	100.00

Source: Primary Data

This study indicates that 87.60% students which is a large percentage are aware that adoption of E-Banking Technology is easily accessible and available anytime anywhere where as 11.60% still feel to some extent it's not available anytime and anywhere due to connectivity and internet coverage and only 0.80% feel that E-Banking to not a solution to anytime anywhere banking. Hence banks have played a good role in making the customers aware of the anytime anywhere banking overall.

TABLE: 6.7. E-BANKING TECHNOLOGIES IS WELL ESTABLISHED IN INDIA

Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	47	18.80
No	203	81.20
Total	250	100.00

Source: Primary Data

The study depicts that 18.80% of the students are of the opinion that India well established with regards to E-Banking Technology where as 81.20% of the students feel India has a long path ahead of before it being called that India is well established when it comes to E-Banking Technology.

TABLE: 6.8. REASONS FOR A CUSTOMER NOT SWITCHING OVER TO E-BANKING TECHNOLOGIES

Frequency	No. of Frequency of Resp.	Percentage
Lack of Knowledge	228	91.20
Network Problem	34	13.60
Fear about Fraud	116	46.40

Source: Primary Data

The study indicates that with regards for the reason behind a customer not switching over to E-Banking Technology many students have multiple opinion, 91.20% feel it is the lack of knowledge where as 13.60% feel that maybe due to Network Problem in a particular area and 46.40% think that customers take a back step due to the fear of fraud. Hence the Banks have a

big task if they need to increase the usage of E-Banking by first imparting the knowledge and getting rid of the fears of frauds.

**TABLE: 6.9. WHAT INITIATIVE SHOULD BANKS TAKE TO POPULARIZE
E-BANKING TECHNOLOGIES AMONG CUSTOMERS**

Frequency	No. of Frequency of Resp.	Percentage
Advertise to create Awareness	248	99.20
Initially provide a Demo to customers	177	70.80
Personal contact programs	56	22.40

Source: Primary Data

The study reveals that 99.20% of the students are of the opinion that appropriate advertisement will increase the usage of E-Banking, 70.80% of students feel that initially a Demo to customer will play an effective role and 22.40% feel that personal contact programs will play an important role. Hence the banks can improve their effectiveness of E-Banking by Advertisements and Initially a Demo.

**TABLE: 6.10. CUSTOMERS SWITCHING OVER TO E-BANKING TECHNOLOGIES
INSTEAD OF TRADITIONAL METHOD**

Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	244	97.60
No	6	2.40
Total	250	100.00

Source: Primary Data

The study indicates that 97.60% of the students i.e. majority of the students are of the opinion that customers should switch over to the E-Banking Technologies instead of Traditional Method where as 2.40% of the students still feel that a switch is not required.

3. SUGGESTIONS

From the above analysis it is clear that the students, those considered as the youth of today will play an important role in the adoption of E-Banking Technology if the banks take adequate measures now itself.

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

(Bi-Monthly) Peer-Reviewed Journal Vol No IV Issues III
APRIL-MAY 2015 ISSN 2278-5655

1. Contact programs as well as initially a demo should be given to a customer when he or she is first introduced to such E-Technology
2. Advertisements and other media should bring awareness of the cost effectiveness as well the convenience caused to customers if E-Banking Technology is adopted.
3. The various security measures adopted by each bank to make the customers experience of E-Banking more safe and secured should be well informed to the customer.
4. Some of the students have suggested in an open ended question in the questionnaire that usage of E-Banking Technology should be a part of the curriculum of the Secondary Education or Higher Secondary Education.

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